

EDUCATION OF HIGH CLASS STUDENTS IN AN AESTHETIC SPIRIT THROUGH LYRIC MUSIC

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ANNOTATION

The content of the article is focused on the study of musical trends that affect the aesthetic psyche of students studying in the upper class. Also, an attempt was made to clearly show the specific characteristics of lyrical music, its aesthetic appeal in terms of pronunciation. It aims to explain the importance of lyrical music in the aesthetic education of high school students with theoretical foundations.

Key words: *aesthetic spirit, musical trends, lyrical music, characteristics, aesthetic appeal, education in aesthetic spirit, theoretical foundations.*

INTRODUCTION: One of the world-renowned industries in our country is the music industry. Teaching people to cook while maintaining their appeal in their own rhythm is the main factor that ensures the sustainability of this industry. Further development of the music industry, continuation of promising plans is being carried out in this field

Working at the Geneva Conservatory created by Emil Jacques-Dalcroze, a Swiss pedagogue who created the system of musical rhythmic education at the end of the 18th century, Dalcroze witnessed that not all students could perform rhythmic movements through clear rhythmic lines. He began to use his relationship with rhythm in his Solfeggio classes. In this regard, he introduces rhythmic gymnastics. In it, all actions were expressed through music.¹

The program "Musical education for secondary schools" was created based on the standards and requirements specified in the prospective state education standard .

¹Karimova DA The importance of rhythmic-motion games in developing students' musical perception.

The main criterion of the program is to educate the child's sense of sophistication, to embody the national spirit, national music tones as much as possible, and to develop the necessary skills and practical skills from music.

The program envisages the gradual implementation of the national values, traditions, folk creativity, musical heritage specific to Uzbekistan at the level of the child's ability to perceive, while preserving the existing pedagogical tasks.

The works and music repertoires recommended in the program are aimed at students' perception of love for the Motherland, hard work, respect for nature, friendship, solidarity, compassion through musical images. In the methodology of musical education, the educational importance of singing is emphasized. Folk songs and games reflecting the national culture help children to feel and perceive the world artistically and enjoy it.

In particular, children of the elementary school will be taught "Oymomo tilla", "Almajon", "Zuv-zuv boragai", "Kichldnajon khish" from children's folk songs, and "Oshkhorakam katar" will be played for the students of the upper grades. "Five Stones", "Oynalik Amon", "This Garden Flower", "White Rice, Blue Rice", "Dastadasta", "Boychechak", "Swallow" during the year. study is recommended.

METHODOLOGICAL ANALYSIS: Musical education is a tool that leads a person to beauty, it forms aesthetic and emotional characteristics of a person. True musical works summarize the aesthetic, moral and political ideas of the time.¹

Human life cannot be imagined without the art of music. Art not only provides spiritual nourishment to people, but also plays an important role in their physical development. Realizing the role of music in moral and aesthetic education, it is necessary not to forget its importance in educating the young generation. Musical beauty is an important factor in the formation of a person's spiritual image.

Music is not an innate desire for beauty, an aesthetic need. It appeared in a person under the influence of work and the environment. With the change of the external world, the person himself also changed, in which he not only progressed

¹Artikov, Tahirjon. Music teaching methodology / T. Artykov; responsible editor O. Azizov. - T.: Muharrir publishing house, 2011. - 6 p

physically, but also spiritually. A person's spiritual ability and, first of all, his aesthetic sense gradually developed and was educated.

Musical-aesthetic education is a much broader concept than musical education. In this process, the music lesson takes an important place, but it does not take a special place. Active development of music perception skills, love for art and beautiful things in life, and the ability to creatively express one's feelings in the language of music play a major role in musical education. When we talk about musical education with a broad pedagogical meaning, it is understood that the entire educational process implemented in the system of educational institutions is organized in accordance with a certain goal. The purpose of well-organized musical education is to form a comprehensively and harmoniously developed person who is ready for work and social activities and always loves the Motherland.

The main goal of teaching music at school is to form a musical culture in students and make them mature people who can meet the demands of the times. The main tasks of teaching music lessons at school are as follows:¹

- to increase students' interest and love for the art of music;
- in the course of musical activities, to develop musical abilities of students, musical learning, voice, attention and feelings of creativity;
- education in moral and aesthetic spirit by means of artistic and ideological content of musical works;
- in music lessons, to direct students to a profession, to form feelings of love for work, love for the Motherland, and respect for adults.

Music is a kind of rich art that creates an image with various sounds and has an ideological and emotional content.

Music aesthetics is a science that studies the essence, artistic forms and styles of musical art.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION; In raising the young generation to become mature in all aspects, along with all the subjects taught at school, the lessons of music

¹GMSaripova, DFAsamova, ZLXhodjayeva. Methodology of music teaching theory and school repertoire. Study guide for students of higher and secondary special educational institutions. TASHKENT-2014 . Page 6.

culture, which is a component of education of sophistication, are of great importance. Music expresses human feelings, dreams and desires in its own artistic language and has an active influence on the child's emotions. Music has a direct impact on learning other subjects at school. Music, as a living art form, reflects the times, life, nature and human feelings, dreams and desires. It makes him happy, married and serves to get food from life.

As the grandfather of our national culture, Abu Nasir Al-Farabi, said, "This science is useful for the health of the body." Our grandfather, Sheikh Saadi, said, "Music is the companion of the human soul."

Therefore, we should start teaching music from elementary school students. Because the foundation of music education is laid in primary school.

The main goal of teaching music at school is to teach high school students the ability to learn the art of music based on the laws of beauty and to inculcate musical culture in them. Lessons of music culture in primary grades are an integral part of the moral-aesthetic education system of general education.

The role of literature and art in educating students in an aesthetic spirit and in developing their artistic taste is extremely large . Because the possibilities of music art are very wide in shaping children's moral standards and strengthening such characteristics as having an active attitude to life. Art not only increases the feelings of high humanity in students, but also effectively affects the spiritual growth of the students.¹

In addition to the specific tasks of musical nature and education, the modern music lesson should also have the following tasks.

The system of musical education at school consists of many elements, such as: music lessons, music education in the classroom and outside of school, vocal and choral studios and clubs, vocal and instrumental ensembles, music schools, etc. In this system, the mass information system occupies a very large place. All the educational and developmental tools form a musical-aesthetic environment in which

¹Artikov, Tahirjon. Music teaching methodology / T. Artykov; responsible editor O. Azizov. - T.: Muharrir publishing house, 2011. - 10 pages.

the student's interests and needs in the field of music arise. The music lesson at school is part of the aesthetic education system, which is largely aimed at the spiritual development of the school student.

Development and enrichment of musical-creative abilities, formation of musical perception skills, interest in musical art, artistic hobby of students should be carried out according to a well-thought-out and consistent system.

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Teaching music in elementary grades aims to accomplish the following tasks:¹

1. To instill in students a love for music and to develop their musical abilities, a sense of rhythm, to form musical learning memory, attention and artistic taste;
2. Cultivating students' love for our national musical heritage and through it for the Motherland;
3. Cultivation of artistic creativity in students.

Today's music teaching methodology is not a suddenly formed science, until now, the formation of this methodology has taken a complex path of development. In the formation of the methodology of music education in our republic, a number of researches of local scientists, methodologists, training manuals, programs, and methodical recommendations were of great importance.

¹GMSharipova, DFAsamova, ZLXhodjayeva. Methodology of music teaching theory and school repertoire. Study guide for students of higher and secondary special educational institutions. TASHKENT-2014. Page 6.

In this educational content, the art and music culture of each region is expressed in its artistic traditions. It should be noted that a full-fledged artistic creation cannot be realized without knowing the life and surrounding beauty. The art of music is an inexhaustible source of aesthetic perception, a fascinating world that conquers the human heart and mind. A person should always strive for beauty and follow these rules of beauty in everyday life.

And for students and young people, music education is very necessary, because the future students will take the teaching profession, educate the young generation in all aspects and bring them to adulthood. In conclusion, we should introduce the young generation, future music teachers, to the music culture of the Uzbek people, develop their sophisticated feelings, and raise the level of music education.

Mohammad Farobiyosh, a scientist among the famous musicians of Central Asia, who has given great importance to the development of music education, expresses many scientific and practical ideas on the issues of education and training of the generation, ethics and aesthetics. He is also the founder of music theory. The famous Tajik scientist, musician, philosopher Jami's book "Risola idarnami muzyka" is written about composition, tone, and rhythm ratios.

A music lesson gives a sense of understanding the joy of music creation, forms a sense of appreciation for beauty, the ability to enjoy the moral-aesthetic content of a composer or folk music. In the lesson, all types of creative activity, which are strongly connected with each other, will be effective.

CONCLUSION: In independent Uzbekistan, to restore the identity of our national culture, it is first of all a good knowledge of our history in order to educate and develop young people in general education schools, as well as to fully understand our present day. Because every innovation is made through historical connection. These are reflected in popular folk tunes and songs, creative activities of singers and composers, status, shashmaqom, epics and today's modern musical activities. These possibilities of musical art serve as a unique, unrepeatable resource for educating the new generation, for the development of the community. From music education, the

new educational content based on state standards ensures the development of students' musical knowledge and skills, such as transferability, memory consolidation, visual imagination, creativity, independence, initiative, artistic and musical taste.

Therefore, "Music culture" lessons are of great importance in educating the young generation. Musical culture lessons have a positive effect on the moral and aesthetic education of students. It increases their sense of beauty, instills love and interest in the art of music, teaches them to love the Motherland, to respect each other, to love work, to appreciate nature, and helps to find one's self in the air.

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